

Task 1) Fazer

Situation: You receive guests to whom you tell about the Finnish company Fazer.

Instructions: First read the text below to yourself. When you are ready, read the text aloud.

Fazer on Pohjoismaiden johtava elintarvikealan yritys.

Fazer valmistaa esimerkiksi leipomotuotteita ja makeisia.

Tuotteista tunnetuin on maitosuklaa: Fazerin Sininen.

Yritys toimii kahdeksassa maassa.

Source: <https://www.fazergroup.com/fi/tietoa-fazerista/>
Pictures: Fazer's picturebank

Task 2) An important place (Monologue)

Situation: You are practicing speaking in a Finnish course. Today, the topic is important places.

Instructions: Describe a place important to you using the questions below. You don't have to answer all of them. Think about which place you want to talk about and let the researcher know when you're ready. Try to keep talking for 2 minutes. Do not share real names, addresses or other details that are too personal.

Why is the place important to you?

What is the best thing about this place? Why?

What do you usually do in this place?

What kind of a place is this?

How long has this place been important to you?

Task 3) Let's get to know each other (Dialogue)

Situation: You're getting to know a new person in a Finnish course.

Instructions: Talk about the following or other topics for 3 minutes. Do not share real names, addresses or other details that are too personal.

- Family
- Living
- Work and study
- Hobbies

Task 4A) Every-day situations (Dialogue)

Situation: You are practicing everyday situations in a Finnish course. One person in the pair is the customer, and the other is the customer service representative.

Instructions: Choose one customer service situation from the list below. Decide who will be the customer and who will be the customer service representative. Talk for about 3 minutes. Do not share real names, addresses or other details that are too personal.

- **Shopping at a grocery store:** The customer tries to pay at the checkout, but their bank card doesn't work, and they have no cash. The cashier sets the items aside and directs the customer to an ATM.
- **Checking into a hotel:** The customer has booked a room, but there are no available rooms at the hotel. The receptionist directs the customer to another hotel.
- **Booking a doctor's appointment:** The customer has booked a doctor's appointment but needs to reschedule due to childcare issues. The receptionist suggests a new time and books a new appointment.
- **Complaint about an online order:** The customer has ordered a camera from an online store, but the package arrives with socks instead. The customer calls the online store's customer service. The customer service representative apologises for the mistake and promises to send a new camera.

Task 4B) Every-day situations (Dialogue)

Situation: You are practicing everyday situations in a Finnish course. One person in the pair is the customer, and the other is the customer service representative.

Instructions: Choose another customer service situation from the list below. Now switch roles: the other person is now the customer and the other the customer service representative. Talk for about 3 minutes. Do not share real names, addresses or other details that are too personal.

- **Shopping at a grocery store:** The customer tries to pay at the checkout, but their bank card doesn't work, and they have no cash. The cashier sets the items aside and directs the customer to an ATM.
- **Checking into a hotel:** The customer has booked a room, but there are no available rooms at the hotel. The receptionist directs the customer to another hotel.
- **Booking a doctor's appointment:** The customer has booked a doctor's appointment but needs to reschedule due to childcare issues. The receptionist suggests a new time and books a new appointment.
- **Complaint about an online order:** The customer has ordered a camera from an online store, but the package arrives with socks instead. The customer calls the online store's customer service. The customer service representative apologises for the mistake and promises to send a new camera.

Task 5) What to pack for a summer trip to an island? (Dialogue)

Situation: You are going on a trip to the archipelago with your Finnish course. You will sleep on the island for 2 nights. It's summer. There is a natural spring on the island where you can get drinking water. There is no store or houses on the island.

Instructions: In addition to food and clothes, you can choose 3 items to pack with you from the items below. Discuss which three items you will take and why. Talk for a maximum of 5 minutes. Do not share real names, addresses or other details that are too personal.

flashlight

tent

water bottle

first-aid kit

matches

knife

Fazer on Pohjoismaiden johtava elintarvikealan yritys.

Fazer valmistaa esimerkiksi leipomotuotteita ja makeisia.

Tuotteista tunnetuin on maitosuklaa: Fazerin Sininen.

Yritys toimii kahdeksassa maassa.

Why is the place important to you?

What is the best thing about this place? Why?

What do you usually do in this place?

What kind of a place is this?

How long has this place been important to you?

- Family
- Living
- Work and study
- Hobbies

flashlight

water bottle

matches

tent

first-aid kit

knife